

MULTIMODAL PREOPERATIVE DIAGNOSIS AND THE EVOLUTION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OPTIONS IN PECTUS EXCVATUM

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Abstract

Pectus excavatum (PE) is the most common congenital thoracic deformity, often leading to functional and psychological impairments. Accurate preoperative diagnosis is essential for selecting the optimal surgical strategy, with multimodal imaging playing a crucial role. This review explores the evolution of diagnostic methods, including radiography, computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, and echocardiography, highlighting their importance in assessing thoracic indices, asymmetry, and cardiopulmonary impact. Additionally, the article traces the history of PE surgical treatment, from early invasive techniques to modern minimally invasive approaches such as the Nuss procedure and hybrid techniques. The advantages, limitations, and complications associated with each surgical method are discussed, emphasizing the need for individualized treatment plans. While significant progress has been made in refining diagnostic and surgical techniques, further research is required to optimize patient outcomes and reduce postoperative complications.

Keywords - Pectus excavatum, Historical review, Thoracic surgery.

Pectus excavatum (PE) is one of the most common types of thoracic deformities, with an incidence of 1:400 births, with a prevailing male gender (4:1), which can influence the development of serious consequences, including scoliosis, heart displacement, the reduction of lung volume, etc. [1].

Preoperative imaging in patients with pectus excavatum is the key diagnostic option, and it is also irreplaceable in guiding the treatment [2]. Chest radiography allows visualization and assessment of the degree of chest wall deformation, leftward shift of the cardiac silhouette, hidden right cardiac border, narrowing of the mediastinum, and inclined anterior ribs. Plain chest radiography can determine different thoracic indices, such as the Welch index, the vertebral index, the xiphoid manubrium corporal index, the Haller index, the correction index, but is not an appropriate option in assessing thoracic asymmetry or sternal torsion [3].

In patients with PE, computed tomography allows the determination of several thoracic indices, which help to assess the severity of the chest wall deformity and to determine the surgical strategy and the selection of the type and size of implants to be used. It should be considered that three-dimensional reconstructions are essential for these decisions, and chest CT scans should be performed at the end of expiration to measure the most severe thoracic indices under conditions similar to those observed by the surgeon in the operating room - the patient being relaxed during expiration [4].

The thoracic index is a formula used to identify or quantify a thoracic deformity or to assess the severity of the defect, the sternal characteristics, the deformity and the impact of PE on the cardiopulmonary function of the patients and to define further treatment strategies.

There is no definition, classification or consensus in the literature where the thoracic index is the gold standard.

The *pectus index (PI)* is the greatest lateral distance of the chest wall relative to the smallest antero-posterior distance between the most depressed point of the chest wall and the vertebral body. Haller J.A. et al. (1987) indicated that a pectus index > 3.25 was present in all patients undergoing surgery, while in patients with mild pectus excavatum who did not undergo surgery, in children and adolescents included in the control group, this index was < 3.25 in all cases. Thus, the authors concluded that the pectus index can be a useful adjacent tool in the objective evaluation of children and adolescents presenting for possible surgical treatment for the pectus excavatum deformity [5]. The significance of the Haller index indicates the ratio between the width of the rib cage and the deepest point of the sternal depression, being the most frequently used index in assessing the severity of PE. In healthy individuals, the Haller index varies between 2.0 and 3.0. However, according to data from recent literature, an index of 3.25 as a cut-off point for surgical intervention is no longer a good discriminator and has no conclusive relationship with the aesthetic problems observed. Meanwhile, the Haller index has other limitations and includes variations in the shape of the chest/age/gender/breathing, lack of assessment of asymmetry and cardiac compression [6, 7, 8].

It has been noticed that minimally invasive repair of pectus excavatum is associated with a high complication rate, which exponentially increases with age and a high Haller index, the principle being exposed in the classification proposed by Clavien-Dindo, where several degrees of this index are described [9].

Degree	Haller Index (cm)
I	3,0 – 3,9
II	4,0 – 4,9
III	5,0 – 5,9
IV	$\geq 6,0$

The second thoracic index that should be included in CT reports is *the correction index*, considered to be a more appropriate criterion in recommending surgical correction, suggested in 2011. In the authors' opinion, this index is very simple to measure, it is easy to reproduce, and represents a very accurate measure that clearly differentiates patients with pectus excavatum from those without the disease. Only at a correction index equal to 10%, the defect should become sufficiently visible to establish the diagnosis. The authors recommend turning to surgical correction of PE for patients with a CI $\geq 28\%$, this value correlating with the long-accepted standard (HI ≥ 3.25) [10, 11].

The asymmetry index (AI) = 1- (the greatest antero-posterior distance of the left chest wall)/ (the greatest antero-posterior distance of the right chest wall), or the ratio of the depth of the left and right chest during inspiration and expiration. In healthy individuals, this index ranges from -0.05 to +0.05. The chest wall is considered "asymmetrical" if the asymmetry index is < -0.05 (the left side of the chest is more convex) or > 0.05

(the right side of the chest is more convex) [12].

The flatness index (FI) was originally suggested by Kim H.C. et al. (2008) for the purpose of assessing depression. In that respect, the eccentricity index (EI), the circularity index (CI) and the rotation index (RI) were developed to assess asymmetry. The ratio of the length between the major axis and the minor axis of an ellipse can represent the degree of flatness of the ellipse. Using this characteristic, the authors proposed the evaluation of a *flatness index*. To calculate this index, the index calculation algorithm finds an ellipse, using the nonlinear least squares fitting method from the extracted inner boundary coordinates of the chest wall. Subsequently, the length of the major axis (Lm) and the length of the minor axis (Ln) of the ellipse are calculated (Fig. 1): $FI = 1 - Ln/Lm$ [13]. The authors also suggested calculating the following indices:

- *The eccentricity index* (EI) = L_f/L_m ;
- *The circularity index* (CI) = L_r/L_m ;

Fig. 1. a) Elements for calculating EI, FI and RI: red line of the chest wall, ellipse marked with blue line extracted with the curve fitting method, Lm - length of the major axis of the ellipse, Ln - length of the minor axis of the ellipse, Lf - distance between two focal points of the ellipse; b) Elements for calculating CI: red line indicates the chest wall, blue line indicates the circle extracted by the curve fitting method, length Lr - radius of the circle (according to Kim H.C. et al., 2008).

The sternal torsion angle (STA) is the angle between the sternum and a horizontal line.

A positive value indicates counter-clockwise rotation of the sternum, and a negative value indicates clockwise rotation. *The Louis angle* (AoL) is the angle between the manubrium and the body of the sternum in the sagittal plane [14].

Computed tomography is the gold standard in the evaluation of the chest in children with PE, but exposure to ionizing radiation remains a concern because children are more sensitive to ionizing radiation. Both inspiratory and expiratory CT have been shown to have a large impact on the assessment of chest motion, with end-expiratory PE assessment leading to an additional number of surgical candidates compared to end-inspiratory assessment alone [15]. Computed tomography is useful in the diagnosis of PE, providing a qualitative assessment of the severity of the chest wall deformity [16]. Considering that standard CT and MRI examinations require breath-holding maneuvers, little is known

about chest wall motion in patients with PE under free breathing conditions. So far, static axial cross-sections of the chest at the deepest point of the funnel have been used to determine the degree of pathology. However, the phase of the respiratory cycle used to calculate the indices is not standardized, although there is evidence that HI and CI change during breathing. A variation in the degree of breathing is likely, especially in children and adolescents, even if a specific phase of breathing is preselected [17]. MRI imaging offers the option to detect and measure chest deformities without radiation, while ultra-fast MRI allows morphometric measurements at different stages of the respiratory cycle [18].

The spirometry results in patients with PE are typically 10% to 20% lower than the population average, and these values are statistically and clinically significant. In addition to altered respiratory biomechanics and some changes in pulmonary function, this chest wall malformation may exert direct compression on the underlying right heart chambers, leading to various

morphological and functional cardiac changes, documented in some studies using echocardiography and cardiac MRI [19].

Common and stress Doppler echocardiography (stress echo) are used in order to demonstrate external cardiac compression (especially of the right ventricle) and its dynamics during rest and stress (exercise), manifested by a reduction in tricuspid annulus diameter and tricuspid/mitral annulus width ratio, a fixed tricuspid valve area at rest and stress, and an increased tricuspid diastolic gradient. It is also important to explore the presence of signs of diastolic dysfunction not only of the right ventricle but also of the left, also assessing the presence of paradoxical septal motion. Therefore, stress echocardiography is necessary to be performed in order to exclude ischemic heart disease or, to a much lesser extent, for other indications, such as valvular heart disease, the exclusion of stress-induced regional wall motion abnormalities [4, 20].

All patients with significant pectus excavatum should undergo an echocardiogram, especially those who are being considered for surgery. Pathological electrocardiographic findings are frequently observed in patients with PE. Observational studies have found several abnormal ECG deviations in patients with PE, such as: P wave abnormalities, right QRS axis deviation, right bundle branch block, T wave inversion, ST segment elevation. It is assumed that these ECG changes are secondary to anatomical distortion, rotation and compression of the heart due to rib cage deformity, mitral valve prolapse or aortic root dilatation, which may require long-term monitoring. However, little is still known about postoperative ECG changes and the association between ECG changes and exercise testing. [21, 22].

The history of the surgical correction of PE starts at the beginning of the 20th century with the works of Meyer L. (1911) and Sauerbruch E.F. (1927). Over the next four decades, some methods were reported by Brown A.L. (1939), Lester C.W. (1946) and others. During this timespan, the suggested surgical therapies were based on the resection of the deformed costal cartilages and sternum, while cutting mediastinal and diaphragmatic adnexa, and/or external traction [23].

More than 80 different surgery types and their modifications for the correction of PE have been described in the literature, of which two types of surgeries are the most widespread: the one first described by Ravitch M.M. (1949), who proposed costochondral osteotomy and the minimally invasive surgery suggested by Nuss D. (1998), which consisted of a temporary implantation of a metal bar aimed to modify the curvature of the anterior chest wall [24, 25].

In 1949, Ravitch M.M., based on the detailed review of Ochsner and DeBaKey (1939), the patient series presented by Lincoln Brown (1940) and the publications of Sweet R.H. (1944) and Lester C.W. (1946) operated on 8 children with PE aged 2 to 10 years. In 7 cases there were no complications, the author achieved excellent results, and one child died due to a fulminant infection. Based on the analysis performed, the author concluded that pectus excavatum is a progressive congenital deformity of the sternum and costal cartilages, which can be satisfactorily corrected by surgery. The

younger the patient, the greater the probability of resulting in a completely normal thoracic contour. Surgery is indicated for the removal of a cosmetic defect that represents a social handicap, for the correction of a skeletal deformity, and for the improvement of cardiac or pulmonary symptoms. Early surgery is important as a prevention of the progression of symptoms and signs. The deformed portions of all involved costal cartilages on both sides are resected. The xiphosternal joint and substernal ligament are divided and the body of the sternum isolated except for its attachment to the manubrium. A transverse osteotomy at the superior margin of the defect allows the sternum to be raised to the corrected position, which is maintained by silk sutures woven into the bone. No external traction is used and no type of cast or other support is required. [26].

In 1965, Ravitch M.M. reaffirmed his basic principles of the operation - subperichondrial excision of all the deformed cartilages, complete release of the sternum by division of the xiphoid and intercostal fascicles, transverse sternal osteotomy, and the absence of external fixation. The author is suggesting a modifying element, which consists in oblique division of the lowermost normal cartilage, which allows osteotomy of the sternum with a space higher than before, and this osteotomy is now always performed on the posterior surface of the sternum. Occasionally, internal fixation or support is used, especially in adolescents or adults with long sternal structures [27].

The subsequent half-century of thoracic surgery was dominated by the technique suggested by Ravitch, which became the gold standard for surgical treatment of pectus excavatum worldwide for that period [28], although several modifications were proposed [29, 30, 31], including modifications designed to maintain the corrected position of the sternum by using a metal support [32, 33]. However, performing the procedure in infants and preschool children resulted in postoperative damage to the growth centers, leading to the development of acquired asphyxiating chondrodystrophy. Therefore, pediatricians were the first to recognize the problem and the number of referrals for pectus excavatum repair decreased significantly during this period [34, 35].

In severe and recurrent types of PE, Robicsek F. (1978) suggested a correction method, which consisted of sternal mobilization, transverse osteotomy, parasternal resection of the costal cartilages (a modified Ravitch procedure), followed by the placement of Marlex prosthetic material behind the sternum and suturing this mesh to the peripheral stumps of the resected ribs, the use of the mesh being intended to support the floating sternum [36]. The modification proposed by Dailey J.F. (1952) consisted of stabilizing the corrected position of the sternum by using an autologous scythe graft [37]. These methods of pectus excavatum repair have been advocated for some time by several authors with relatively satisfactory early results, even though there was a risk for the appearance of the chest wall to alter over time. [38].

In 1970, Wada J, et al. published a study in which they presented the results of 271 surgeries performed on patients with PE using the "sterno-turnover" procedure, which consists of separating the sternum from the

mediastinal tissue by blunt dissection, the ribs or costal cartilages and intercostal muscles are transected bilaterally at the level of the costal arches along the edge of the deformity, with the deformed sternum being then elevated, with both internal mammary arteries ligated and sectioned. After the sternum is sectioned and removed en bloc, thoracoplasty is resorted to by the method of inverting the sternum with its fixation with steel wire and each costal cartilage or rib is sutured with silk to the adjacent cartilage. Since the surgical results obtained in cases using the sterno-turnover procedure were not satisfactory, the authors also resorted to costoplasty, which provided that the ribs were straightened through multiple partial incisions or wedge resections and then reattached anteriorly to the sternum to form a new and elevated costal arch [39]. The so-called turnover operation for pectus excavatum was disappointing due to postoperative complications, such as fistula formation with necrosis of the bones and muscles. For this reason, Taguchi T.K. et al. (1975) developed a new sternal turnover operation with preservation of the bilateral internal mammary vessels, the surgical intervention being useful for patients over 15 years of age [40].

Some modifications have been suggested in severe cases of PE associated with Marfan syndrome, Javangula K.C. et al. (2006) proposed the use of a "sternal lodge" with 2 wide strips of Gortex patch as an alternative to a metal bar [41], and in cases of PE and annuloaortic ectasia, Kawamura T. et al. (2011) reported an open approach by partial sternotomy and sterno-costochondroplasty to divide and refix the right and left ribs, which was advantageous in partially immobilizing the sternum so that the right ribs could be opened to expose the deviated mediastinum [42].

Buchwald J. et al. (2020) suggested a modification of the Ravitch procedure, the difference being that the ends of the resected cartilages are blade-shaped to allow them to be inserted into previously prepared wedge-shaped depressions, which are located on both edges of the sternum. The correction technique proposed by the authors does not require the use of additional sternal support, and the good long-term results make the procedure suitable and acceptable in the treatment of anterior chest wall deformity in children and adolescents [43].

Over the recent decades, the Nuss procedure has gained wide acceptance in the surgical correction of patients diagnosed with PE [44]. According to Nuss D., Kelly R.E. (2010), the minimally invasive repair proposed by Nuss D. can be successfully performed in patients aged between 1 and over 50 years, the ideal age being before puberty because at this age the thorax is still malleable, the support bar is adjusted in length during puberty, and the recovery time is short, with a low incidence of relapses. Excellent results and a short recovery time have been recorded in patients under 8 years of age, but because the support bar is removed before puberty, which is a period of growth spurt, there is a potential for relapse. However, in cases where significant cardiac and/or pulmonary compression is noted, early repair is warranted, but the bar should be left in situ for 3 years. The family should also be in-

formed that the patient may require a second bar placement either at the time of removal of the first bar or if a longer bar is required [45].

Specific inclusion criteria, originally established for the Nuss procedure and relevant to patient selection, include two or more of the following: 1) A computed tomography (Haller) index greater than 3.25 or correction index of 10% or greater in association with cardiac or pulmonary compression; 2) Pulmonary function test results clearly showing restrictive and/or obstructive insufficiency; 3) Cardiologic evaluation showing cardiac compression, displacement, mitral valve prolapse, murmur, or conduction abnormalities; 4) Documenting the progression of the deformity with advancing age in association with the development or worsening of physiological symptoms (i.e., shortness of breath, lack of endurance, exercise intolerance, palpitations, and chest pain); 5) Psycho-social effects. The optimal age range for pectus excavatum repair appears to be between 10 and 14 years, when the chest wall is still malleable [46, 47].

The procedure developed by D. Nass et al. (1998), who first published the results of the treatment of patients operated on with pectus excavatum over a period of 10 years, consists of using an original surgical technique based on the "extension" of the costal cartilages due to their elasticity against the background of dysplasia using a metal plate inserted retrosternal. In the opinion of the authors, the minimally invasive technical procedure proposed by them has some obvious advantages, such as: 1) the lack of anterior incision of the chest wall, does not require extensive dissection and detachment of the musculo-fascial component of the anterior chest wall and the lack of resection of the costal cartilages or sternal osteotomy; 2) short operating time, minimal blood loss and early return to full activity; 3) long-term normal thoracic resistance, expansion, flexibility and elasticity; and 4) excellent long-term cosmetic result [48]. With excellent cosmetic results, this minimally invasive procedure has quickly become the standard of care for the treatment of children and adolescents with PE [47]. Although minimally invasive correction has been successfully performed in patients from 1 to over 50 years of age, according to D. Nuss, the ideal age for this intervention is just before puberty, because at that age the chest is malleable, the support bar is fixed during the pubertal growth spurt, the recovery time is short, and the incidence of relapse is low. Patients younger than 8 years of age, including those aged 3-6 years, have an excellent result and a short recovery time, but because the support bar is removed before the pubertal growth spurt, there is a potential for relapse. However, if a younger patient has significant cardiac and/or pulmonary compression, early repair is warranted, but the bar should be left in situ for 3 years, and the family should be informed that the patient may require a second bar placement when a longer bar is needed [45, 48]. Park H.J. et al. (2012) found that routine early repair of pectus excavatum in patients older than 3 years is safe and effective.

Currently, several significant changes have been made to the technical procedure that Nuss originally patented, which led to the creation of "hybrid" methods, which can not only compete with the original method,

but in some respects even surpass it [50, 51, 52, 53]. The original procedure proposed by Donald Nuss was performed without the aid of thoracoscopy, later this technique was modified to be performed with the help of a thoracoscope as part of measures to improve the safety of the intervention [54, 55], this modification having the potential to reduce the risk of cardiac complications without increasing the rate of minor complications [56]. In 2014, Dawn E. Jaroszewski modified the Nuss procedure, describing an original technique for forced mechanical elevation of the sternum (sternal retraction) with expansion of the retrosternal space and facilitating blunt dissection of the anterior mediastinum in severe cases of pectus excavatum and safe passage of the metal bar, using a special “crane” device and a metal suture tied to the sternum without the need for endoscopic guidance [57]. Subsequently, the advantage of using the sternal retraction technique was confirmed by several authors [58, 59]. Rygl M. et al. (2014) used a technical innovation using a semiflexible thoracoscope and hook-lift of the sternum, reducing the risk of cardiac injury [60], and Haecker F.M. et al. (2019) used a vacuum bell to lift the sternum [61].

In the standard Nuss procedure for pectus excavatum, the costal arch is often lifted together with the sternum, resulting in unevenness of the lower chest. Postoperative protrusion of the costal arch can be prevented by the original change suggested by Nagasao T. et al. (2023), which involves separating the seventh costal cartilage from the sternum. Wu L. et al. (2024), in order to ensure sufficient sternal elevation, suggested horizontal separation of the sternum after rotating the metal bar, which also contributes to reducing postoperative pain [62, 63].

Even though the Nuss procedure is considered minimally invasive, some technical problems have been noticed, the most important of which is the challenge of mediastinal manipulation in a severely sunken sternum, and the precordial elevation may cause some intraoperative adverse events, such as rib fracture. The overall incidence of minor and major complications after this procedure ranges between 2-20%, the real incidence of life-threatening complications and mortality being unknown, since the total number of procedures performed worldwide is unknown [64]. Some fatal complications have been described during the Nuss procedure, after the procedure itself, and during removal of the metal bar after certain amounts of time, such as pneumothorax, hemothorax, pleural effusions, cardiac perforation, etc [55, 64]. Metal allergy is found in 2.7% and 3.1% of patients, manifesting as rash, erythema, granuloma, postoperative wound problems, or pleural effusion [65]. The surgical technique, patient age, severity and asymmetry of the pectus, previous chest surgery, and surgeon experience play a decisive role in the overall incidence of such complications [66]. In 2017, Masai K. et al. developed a combined Ravitch and Nuss technique for the treatment of severe PE, which involves three steps: 1) the severely depressed portion of the costal cartilage is transected; 2) the sternum is stabilized with pectus bars, and 3) the anterior chest wall is then reconstructed. Mercedes incisions are cut in the deepest part of the thorax. After mobilization

of the pectoralis and rectus muscles, the deformed costal cartilages are exposed. Then, bilaterally, the ribs from the third or fourth to the seventh costal cartilage junction were disconnected from the adjacent sternum. The bilateral internal mammary arteries were preserved. According to the original Ravitch procedure, transverse sternal osteotomy at the level of the third rib can be used if necessary. With the dissection of the costal cartilage of the bilateral ribs, the buried sternum developed increased mobility (part of the Ravitch procedure). After mobilization of the sternum, the Nuss procedure was performed. Under the control of a thoracoscope, the inserter was safely positioned under the sternum. Subsequently, a titanium pectus bar was passed through the mediastinum under the reconstructed sternum and then rotated 180 degrees to stabilize the anterior chest wall. Because the cut ends of the costal cartilages protruded approximately 1–2 cm due to the elevation of the anterior chest wall, it was necessary to resect the edge of the costal cartilages to level the anterior wall of the rib cage, after which the edge of the costal cartilage and the sternum were sutured using surgical metal wires or sutures [67]. Some combined techniques have been suggested for the repair of asymmetrical cases of pectus excavatum, such as the procedure proposed by Kuyama H. et al. (2021), which involves chondrotomy of the depressed and deformed costal cartilage to elevate the depressed part, combined with the Nuss procedure or the technique presented by Okuyama H. et al. (2021), which provides for thoracoscopic excision of the costal cartilage combined with the Nuss procedure [68, 69].

Therefore, even with protocols with promising preliminary results, in order to improve the success rates of the surgical correction of patients with pectus excavatum, the need for additional studies with the evaluation of long-term results is imposed [70]. Several meta-analyses have been reported in the specialty literature, which aimed to comparatively evaluate the effectiveness of the Ravitch and Nuss surgical procedures in the repair of pectus excavatum [71, 72, 73]. The comparative analysis presented by the authors could not definitively suggest a preference for any of the surgical method of pectus excavatum repair [74]. The Nuss procedure was associated with a shorter operative time and diminished blood loss compared with the Ravitch procedure, while the postoperative length of hospital stay was similar. No difference was observed between the procedures in terms of overall complication rates, while the rates of reoperation due to rod migration or persistent deformity, postoperative pneumothorax, and hemothorax were higher in the Nuss group than in the Ravitch group [75].

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